

CHALLENGES OF CHOOSING EXERCISES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND ITS TYPOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6272132>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 13th february 2022

Accepted: 18th february 2022

Online: 23th february 2022

KEY WORDS

Exercises, issues and challenges, creation, motivation, activities, system, communication.

ABSTRACT

To be a good teacher, teachers are encouraged to apply the practice of “reflective mind” to have an understanding of what is going on in the classroom and to understand what is working and what will happen or does not work (Farrell, 2018). Teachers, especially English teachers face different problems not only in teaching and the competitive English language learning in education, but also to the demanding nature of the teaching profession. This article is intended to give basic information about major problems in choosing appropriate exercises in teaching English and conducting the classes. Being aware of problems and challenges in teaching can shape the personal and professional growth of teacher-trainees in a real learning environment and can be a good resource to move forward and succeed in teaching profession.

In modern methodology, the process of learning foreign languages is considered as a continuous chain of exercises consistently performed. The quality of the exercises affects the success of mastering speech activity in a foreign language. Exercises, based on the activity nature of learning foreign languages, act as a form of communication language material and the implementation of the objectives of learning. In other words, exercises are not only a means of mastering linguistic material, but also a means of mastering various types of speech activity.

The notion of “system” implies the presence of a certain set of elements, parts that are combined in a certain way. Elements and parts of the system have a specific function. They are characterized by the presence of strong links between the elements of the system. These bonds, moreover, ensure its stability and integrity. The exercise system provides:

- a) selection of the necessary exercises, appropriate to the character of a particular skill or skill;
- b) determining the required sequence of exercises;

c) the correct location of the material and its ratio;

d) systematicity (regularity) of a certain material and certain exercises;

e) correct interrelation (correlation and interaction) of different types of speech activity among themselves and within themselves.

In methodical science, exercise is considered differently. Some scientists consider it a structural unit of the methodical organization of educational material. Others see it as a unit for learning foreign language speech activity. Exercises implement a variety of teaching methods, create favorable conditions for the development of speech skills in the foreign language. Exercises can be performed in various conditions. If the students' attention is directed to the content, and not to the language form, then in this case they perform speech actions associated with the expression of their own thoughts or with an understanding of the thoughts given by the author of the text (in listening or reading). Psychologists understand as an exercise the repeated fulfillment of certain actions or activities with the aim of mastering them, based on understanding and accompanied by conscious control and adjustment (L. B. Itelson). I. L. Bim sees in exercise the minimum unit for organizing the student's learning activities in mastering the elements of a foreign language system. Units of instruction personify the way in which units of material are used directly in students' performance.

The results of foreign language teaching are determined primarily through a system of exercises, because the practical goal of learning a foreign language is to

master all types of speech activities through exercises. So what is exercise? Exercise refers to individual or sequential operations or actions aimed at acquiring a specific activity or improving that activity in a learning situation. The requirements for the exercises are that they should be adequate to the skills and competencies they are developing. If the training exercises do not have a verbal character, the acquired skills and abilities will not have a communicative character. Therefore, speech promotion should be based on speech situations only. This means that speaking skills and competencies should be developed not in language exercises, but in speech-oriented exercises that reflect or are close to that speech and communicative activity. We can see different classifications of exercises in the methodological literature. It is based on different principles.

According to the principle of communication, we can distinguish three types of exercises:

1. Non-verbal exercises.

2. Speech-Oriented Exercises: a) Phonetic, grammatical and lexical exercises according to language aspects. b) Creative exercises.

3. Real speaking exercises.

One of the most important exercises in building skills is speech. Real speaking exercises, on the other hand, help build speech skills in all types of speech activities. Non-verbal exercises are divided into two types: language exercises and pre-speech exercises. Language exercises are multi-faceted and focus on the study of language phenomena. M: Make a whole sentence from parts (words), make a gap according to the rules, change the structure

of the sentence based on the transformation, and others. We will now look at language and speech skills exercises.

The most common types of exercise today are:

1. Exercises for training or exercise or exercise.
2. Creative speaking exercises.

The first includes language exercises (lexical, phonetic, grammatical). Their characteristic feature is that they do not focus on the formation of speech skills, but on the study of the form of linguistic phenomena. This means that they cannot be speech exercises because they cannot automate the use of language material by students in speech. All preparatory exercises aimed at training and automating language units outside of speech activities are called pre-speech exercises. These include exercises based on substitution and imitation.

Speech exercises.

They are divided into pure speech exercises and speech-oriented exercises. They are educational speech exercises and aspect-oriented exercises (ie, phonetic, grammatical, lexical).

Objectives: 1) Separate automation of language events in addition to speech activities. 2) Analytical exercises (receptive, reproductive) consisting of language exercises, sentence construction in accordance with the intended purpose and rule, analysis of language phenomena, transformation, etc. One of the most important exercises in developing speech skills is speech therapy. They are learning exercises. Such exercises take into account, on the one hand, the specifics of the type of speech activity being studied, and, on the

other hand, the aspects of the language material that are difficult for the learners.

Despite its communicative orientation, it would be wrong to say that the process of teaching a foreign language is artificially based on purely informative motivation. Therefore, it is incorrect to call exercises in artificial conditions purely communicative exercises. As a result, some Methodists deny using them in the teaching process. The reason is that they are not informative. Others, for a long time, limit themselves to pure speech exercises and forget that they are not only in speech activity, but also in teaching and learning. Not only is it a teaching tool for reading, but it is also a teaching tool for other types of speaking activities (i.e., speaking and writing). Thus, skill development exercises can be classified as follows. Depending on the reason: exercises on the situation, the topic, a fragment of the topic, the text, the relationship with the text, the use of visual aids.

According to the stages of formation of skills:

1. Pre-speech language exercises.
2. Training exercises and the creation of automatisms.
3. Exercises to use language material in changing situations.

It should be noted that speech skills are a component of character and speech skills. In foreign language teaching, the main goal is to develop speaking skills. Exercises that build speech skills are important to clarify communicative approach and tasks. They are exercises that teach the use of language phenomena for communicative purposes.

It is known that the main feature of speech skills is shown in the following.

1. Creative use of language phenomena, language material in accordance with the communicative approach, goals and conditions aimed at solving problems:

2. Natural motivation to use a foreign language in a particular type of speech activity. For example: native language and foreign language this is done differently.

3. Automate the movement of speech in the use of language material, ie focus on the content, not the form of language.

4. Ease of performing complex speech actions, purposefulness. (compactness, mobility, perfection, automation, stability, etc.)

Hence, exercises that form speech skills should meet the following requirements:

1. Based on natural motivation as much as possible.

2. Related language material should be monologue or dialogic, oral and written.

3. It should be aimed at teaching students to use the learned language material in all types of speaking activities.

4. Each type of speech activity should take into account its specific characteristics.

Also, there are basic types of exercises in modern teaching system such as:

- A) Non-verbal exercises.
- B) Speech exercises.
- C) Analytical language exercises
- D) Speech-oriented exercises
- E) Pure speech mask.
- F) Grammar and Vocabulary.

Grammar and Vocabulary exercises are divided into 2 parts depending on the

language in which they are performed. One-language and two-language exercises. Depending on the form of execution, it can be oral or written. There are different types of speaking activities, exercises that teach listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

In conclusion, as for this article, the goal was to identify the problems and challenges in choosing exercises during English lessons. The findings showed that teachers should draw attention to use essential, useful materials that are related to the topic of the lesson and have to be more attentive their own voice, class management, teaching strategies, learning strategies, English communication, vocabulary, lesson planning, teaching assessment, and class motivation played a role in the complexity of education. Looking back, it seems that the interns thought you knew everything is an incorrect assumption. The indicator is that no matter how long one has been in the teaching profession, a The teacher works in the teaching profession, problems and difficulties are inevitable. In fact, even Although teachers are trained to teach and teach, not everyone has this quality a good language teacher, especially if the teaching tool is not their first language. As linguists Renandya and Widodo (2016) pointed out, "teachers need to be trained and retrained by changing language learning needs". So, the effectiveness of useful exercises in teaching in a real learning environment can be personal and lead professional growth. In general, teachers learn every day to understand their students' knowledge ability to adapt to their needs and how complex the learning situation is. Above, in general, teaching is dynamic in nature and influenced by students' learning styles.

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